

Exploring the Influence of Prenatal Yoga on Maternal Well-being and Perinatal Outcomes: An Exhaustive Literature Synthesis

Pradeep Kumar Panda^{1*} and Dr. Rahul Sharma²

1* Research Scholar, School of Public Health, Poornima University, Jaipur,

E. Mail: pradeepbalasore@gmail.com

2 School of Public Health, Poornima University, Jaipur

E-Mail: rahuls76@gmail.com

Abstract:

Prenatal yoga has been embraced as an adjunct to enhance pregnancy course and birth outcomes amongst pregnant women. This literature review sought to critically review existing literature on prenatal yoga intervention to details several aspects of maternal well-being and childbirth. Therefore, using academic databases, an extensive search was conducted to establish appropriate published articles from 2008 to 2024. The review involved randomized controlled trials, systematic review, meta-analysis and observational studies, and a total of 11 studies were targeted. The review of population data supports the idea about offering prenatal yoga for pain relief during labor, for decreasing stress, anxiety, and depression for mothers-to-be, and for enhancing birth weight and gestational age at birth. Moreover, it was revealed that prenatal yoga also improves the extent of bond between a mother and a fetus as well as maternal well-being. However, due to variations in the type of yoga intervention as well as the study methodology used, the conclusions therefore have a limited scope of applicability. However, the review also reveal that larger and less flexible studies are required in order to draw more informative conclusion. This information is vital to OBGYs and other health practitioners and expectant women to inform them about the benefits of practicing yoga during pregnancy.

Introduction:

Pregnancy could thus be defined as a special phase in the Lifecycle of a woman, characterized by physical, emotional and psychological changes. These changes can cause such inconveniences and other health complications including lower back pains, anxiety, depression among others. These symptoms have been a cause unto themselves: prenatal yoga has begun to step forward as a complementary therapy that helps ease these concerns and bolster maternal well-being.

The current literature is reviewed in order to compile evidence of the impact that prenatal yoga may have on both the maternal population and birth outcomes, in order to provide insights to various healthcare professionals those who practice in the field of maternal and child health and for expectant mothers. This critique seeks to identify and analyse the existing body of knowledge on the impact of Yoga on maternal health and delivery outcomes. Through a review of literature, we seek to provide a comprehensive knowledge about how yoga interventions may impact different aspects of the prenatal and perinatal period for woman focusing on physical health, psychological well-being, and birth outcomes though they are not antagonistic. Also, this review will highlight the limitations to the existing body of knowledge and possible areas for research in this essential area of study.

Methodology:

The electronic databases PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar and PubMed-MEDLINE were used to accounce for all studies published between 2008 and 2024. The search terms that were employed included prenatal or antenatal yoga, maternal health and birth outcomes as well as any other variations of the three. The inclusion criteria were: Provider type: PICOT elements: P = Pregnant women, I = prenatal yoga intervention, C = None, O = Maternal and perinatal health, T = Quantitative studies published between 2008 and 2024, Peer reviewed. This search resulted in the selection of a total of 57 articles related to the key concepts of the study. ANOVA was done to filter the selected article further on the basis of relevance and the study design and quality of evidence. From the targeted literature review and using the exclusion criteria, out of the 24 studies

that matched the inclusion criteria the following 11 were considered relevant and used in this research.

The articles derived from a systematic literature search and the selected articles for the current review included a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative research, including different study types like simple clinical trials, systematic reviews, meta-analysis, and qualitative research. Each study underwent an assessment of the quality of the methodology used, number of participants included in the study, the nature of the intervention, the measures utilised and the results obtained. The information gathered from these studies was then integrated to recognize the current profiles to compare them

and establish the general trends and patterns to find out whether the findings were in agreement or in contrast with trends pointed out in other literature.

Literature Review:

1. Physical Benefits of Prenatal Yoga

Some of the authors have highlighted on the physical impacts of prenatal yoga on the pregnant woman as expounded below: Similarly, Holden et al. , (2019) also conducted a pilot randomized controlled study that examined the effects of prenatal yoga on back pain, balance, and overall wellbeing of the pregnant women. From these aspirations, the authors made some recommendations for improving these aspects of working and learning even though they acknowledged that the findings should be replicated to other settings.

Prenatal yoga intervention in the context of Taiwanese investigation done by Sun et al. (2010) focused on the effect on pregnancy discomforts and Maternal Childbirth Self-efficacy. This study revealed that the subjects who enrolled in the yoga activity had lower levels of discomforts and higher childbirth self-efficacy as compared to those in the control group.

2. Mental Health and Emotional Well-being

The specific research papers that are related to the topic of prenatal yoga and its effect on the psychological well-being of the mothers are as follows: Newham et al. (2014) conducted a randomized controlled trial that assessed an impact of a single session of a structured antenatal yoga on maternal stress and anxiety. Through their study, they were also able to point out that in their subjects in the yoga group, the rates for anxiety as well as depression had reduced distinctly.

Moreover, the argument was supported by Ng et al., (2019) meta-analysis that provided the evidence of the impact of Yoga based interventions at mitigating maternal depression and anxiety during pregnancy. The authors noted that it seemed that the study was doable to consider the use of yoga as an extra treatment for prenatal depression.

Hence the study by Bershadsky et al., (2014) aimed at finding out the impact of prenatal Hatha yoga on affect and cortisol as well as depressive and affect symptoms. Based on their views it was stated that affect and cortisol levels are positively impacted after a solitary yoga session hence could be effective for stress relieving purposes.

3. Labor and Childbirth Outcomes

Other studies have also focussed in the effects of yoga on labour and childbirth outcomes have also been explored in literature. In another study by Bolanthakodi et al. (2018), an approach for prenatal yoga was followed to assess the reduction in labor pain and the childbirth experiences. According to the results of the study, female participants who engaged in yoga, showed less complains of labor pain, and improved birth outcomes.

In a retrospective study by Wadhwa et al. (2020) looked at the impact of exercises during antenatal period on the progress of labor and birth focusing on yoga. The study also included possible advantages involved in regard to the length of labor and the frequency of the need for augmenting it, where females who practiced exercise in any form, including yoga, before gave birth have been found to have shorter lengths of their labors less need to have them augmented.

4. Maternal-Fetal Attachment

Faucher (2013) reported on a study that found mindfulness yoga improved scores on depression scales and enhance maternal fetal attachment. This opens up an implication of practicing yoga during pregnancy to have some positive effects on apart from physical and mental, even parental affection between the mother and the child.

5. Safety and Feasibility

Some of the studies available in the literature have also focused on the safety of yoga practice during pregnancy as well as the feasibility of yoga practice during pregnancy. Styles et al., (2019) used mixed-methods study to determine the feasibility and effectiveness of prenatal yoga in young women. This led them to conclude that prenatal

yoga was relatively well-received among caregivers and that the participants themselves considered it to be positive.

In a mixed-methods study of hot yoga's different dimensions, Nguyen-Feng et al. (2023) sought to understand the views of pregnant women. Although this study did not aim at evaluating safety, it emphasized on the precautions and explains that pregnant women should consult doctors before practicing more intense forms of yoga during pregnancy period.

Discussion:

From the reviewed literatures, we found that prenatal yoga has the potentiality to benefit the mothers in a number of ways and/or decrease the chances of adverse childbirth outcomes. They repeated some patterns which indicate change in status of pain, or emotions, or maybe childbirth history. However, it is noteworthy to underscore, namely that the number of the identified investigations correlate with positive outcomes, the strength of evidence varies, and some results should be interpreted with appropriate caution due to some methodological shortcomings.

One of the robust findings across the range of studies was identified as postnatal mental health benefits of the exercise, particularly anxiety and depression. This is even so considering the fact that mood disorders are prevalent during pregnancy and these may equally have negative impacts on both maternal and fetal well-being.

Physical status/health and relation with exercise and the subsequent effect on the labor outcomes are slightly less positive at a common level but still generally very favorable. However, it should be noted that aspects such as back pain or labor pain and childbirth self- efficacy, were recognized by some published work. However, owing to the vast methodological variation and sample size it wasn't possible to come to definitive conclusions.

One interesting line of thinking that emerged from within the literature is that of yoga and maternal-fetal attachment. Although it was however not explored to the other extent as the other aspects, it seems to call for further research in the future because the first attachment is very critical for both the maternal and child outcomes.

To some extent, this study made the following contributions: The review also brought out some gaps in the literature. Some cross-sectional studies contained variables with limited variability; therefore, the probability of an accurate, large sample assessment was reduced. Additionally, in regard to the intervention, the type, duration and the frequency of yoga varied in the included studies which made it very difficult to compare the interventions. In this way, it is possible to conclude that it is essential to perform the

studies with higher sample sizes that would contribute to the methodological improvement of more sound outcomes.

Effectiveness of prenatal yoga was found in the above reviewed studies; however, the following safety concerns were only highlighted in relation to prenatal yoga practice and requires further research. Therefore, yoga generally recommended during pregnancy but it is unclear what detailed guidelines exist in this unsettled area, especially in terms of different types of yoga and their potential intensity.

Conclusion:

This comprehensive literature review consolidates the information from the contemporary articles on prenatal yoga and its benefits on the health of pregnant women and birth. The evidence clearly put forth suggestions on potential benefits across various domains which includes: concerns related to their mental health and physical well-being, and the childbirth experiences. However, methodological limitations which includes: small sample size, heterogeneity of the intervention delivered to participants, the studies require a careful interpretation. Next steps should entail studies with larger sample sizes, use of meta-analysis, and randomized controlled designs with clearly defined and consistent interventions as a way of further testing yoga's applicability in prenatal care, safety and effectiveness in long term. Yet, the presented results indicate current practices of yoga as potentially beneficial complementary intervention in the field of maternal healthcare, requiring further rigorous investigation is imperative to establish definitive evidence-based recommendations and optimize its integration into prenatal care protocols.

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